

unitless), a better Zn fertility index, SP at 15° and 30°C were calculated: $SP = (q.C)^{1/2} \cdot (K_1 \cdot K_2)^{-1/4}$. Because SP reflected the physicochemically defined soil Zn supply, but not Zn supply to the crop under the influence of Cu, Fe, and Mn, which may compete with Zn at root exchange sites, SPs were corrected to CSP = (SP). $(\sum M_{Zn} \cdot M^{-1} Cu, Fe, Mn)$, where M was μ moles of 0.005M DTPA (pH 7.3)-extractable respective soil nutrients.

Each of 20 soils was used at 5 kg/pot. Twice replicated treatments were 0, 5, 10, or 15 ppm Zn as ZnSO₄. Six 20-d-old Jaya seedlings were grown for 60 d in each of 160 pots, and percent yield was calculated for each soil:

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{yield with 0 ppm Zn (g)}}{\text{yield with adequate Zn (g)}} \times 100.$$

Percent yield varied from 73 to 103%. None of C and q at 15° and 30°C and their averages were related to percent yield, showing that neither measure could define Zn fertility (Table 1). Percent yield and SP correlations were not significant because of widely spaced ideal bands of points in plots of percent yield versus SP. Bands merged in an ideal curve in plots of percent yield versus CSP and were significantly correlated, thus emphasizing the need to correct SP. Critical limits of soil Zn as CSP at 15° and 30°C and average CSP were 1.45, 1.27, and 1.17. Because CSPs included a factor of competitive influence of Cu, Fe, and Mn on Zn availability, they appeared to be a potentially better fertility index than SPs.

All CSPs correlated well with Zn concentration in III 1 b, which is normally recommended tissue for analysis of Zn nutrition status (Table 2). In relation to CSP, tissues could be arranged in reliability order for tissue analysis, CSP at 15°: III 1 b > S > III 1 b > 1s, CSP at 30° C: S > III 1 b and average CSP: S > III 1 b > 1s. Zinc concentration in IIb, IV 1 b, R, and WS did not correlate significantly to CSP, thus were unsuitable for tissue analysis. Total Zn uptake correlated significantly with CSP, except CSP at 15°C. Because of the highest correlation coefficient, the CSP at 15°C and analysis of III 1 b were recommended to know Zn status in soils and plants. □

Table 1. Correlation coefficients (r) between percent yield and Zn fertility parameters.

Zn fertility parameters	Range	r
C at 15°C (μ g/10 ml)	0.07-2.74	0.121
C at 30°C (μ g/10 ml)	0.13-0.77	0.122
Average C (μ g/10 ml)	0.13-1.50	0.142
q at 15°C (μ g/g soil)	5.41-30.28	0.056
q at 30°C (μ g/g soil)	5.34-29.70	0.068
Average q (μ g/g soil)	5.37-29.99	0.068
SP at 15°C (unitless)	0.53-4.29	0.237
SP at 30°C (unitless)	0.57-2.76	-0.109
Average SP (unitless)	0.69-2.76	0.129
CSP at 15°C (unitless)	0.32-2.48	0.783*
CSP at 30°C (unitless)	0.35-2.49	0.563*
Average CSP (unitless)	0.42-2.21	0.758*

*Significant at p = 0.05.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients (r) between Zn concentration in rice tissues and significant Zn fertility parameters.

Tissue	r		
	CSP at 15°C	CSP at 30°C	Average CSP
First leaf blade from top (IIb)	0.320	0.370	0.384
Second leaf blade from top (IIIb)	0.534*	0.424	0.438
Third leaf blade from top (III 1 b)	0.790*	0.465*	0.711*
Fourth leaf blade from top (IV 1 b)	-0.051	0.071	0.007
Leaf sheath (1s)	0.446*	0.440	0.507*
Stem (S)	0.593*	0.733*	0.735*
Root (R)	0.022	0.124	0.078
Whole shoot (WS)	0.263	-0.014	0.149
Total Zn uptake in shoot	0.373	0.484*	0.475*

*Significant at p = 0.05.

Effect of applying lac-coated or non-coated urea on rice grain yield

S. K. Sahu, and S. S. Pal, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

We compared the efficiency of lac-coated (33% N) and noncoated (46% N) urea in 1981 and 1982 wet seasons. Soil was a clay loam (Typic Aquept) with pH 5.8, 0.63% organic carbon, and electrical conductivity 0.09 mmho/cm. Jaya was planted in poorly drained soil at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda. There were nine treatments in a randomized block design with four replications. Lac-coated urea was applied at transplanting. Noncoated urea was applied at transplanting, and at 21 and 55d after transplanting (DT). The crop received 60-17-25 kg NPK/ha.

Applying lac-coated urea at 40 kg N/ha at transplanting followed by non-coated urea at 20 kg N/ha at 55 DT sig-

nificantly increased grain yield over other treatments (see table). □

Effect of lac-coated and noncoated urea on grain yield of Jaya, Orissa, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	1981	1982		
Transplanting				
40	20	0	3.8	4.0
40	0	20	4.0	4.3
20	20	20	4.2	4.3
60	0	0	4.0	4.1
40 ^a	20	0	3.9	4.4
40 ^a	0	20	5.1	4.6
20 ^a	20	20	4.5	4.4
60 ^a	0	0	4.4	4.3
Control			3.1	3.2
CD at 5%			0.6	0.2

^a Lac-coated urea.

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